

PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.2
**Modelli numerici per la
simulazione del
comportamento di
elementi /edifici rinforzati**

NOVEMBRE 2025

Poročilo 1.2
**Numerični modeli za
simulacijo obnašanja utrjenih
konstrukcijskih elementov
in stavb**

NOVEMBER 2025

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PRO-SIS

Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.2

Numerical models for the simulation of the behavior of reinforced elements/buildings

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Numerical models for the simulation of the behavior of reinforced elements/buildings

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1. Introduction

The report collects the results of Activity 1.2 of the PRO-SIS project, aimed at the Development of numerical models capable of simulating the actual behaviour of experimental samples tested in the CONSTRAIN project.

Within the CONSTRAIN project (INTERREG V-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2014-2020 - <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>), strategies to reduce the seismic vulnerability of existing masonry were developed and tested in an extended experimental campaign. The developed strengthening method is based on the use of mortar coatings reinforced by fiber-based composite materials. The main advantage of the developed system is that it can be applied only on one side of the wall, which makes it much more convenient for residents and businesses. Due to construction works only on the outside of the building, people and their belongings don't have to be relocated, and business activity doesn't have to be interrupted. Furthermore, valuable artistic decorations can be preserved on the inside (or outside, when the inside side application is preferred). The developed strengthening method stands out because of its proven effectiveness by tests on structural components and on full scale pilot building.

The aim of the "PRO-SIS" project (INTERREG VI-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2021-2027 - <https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/pro-sis>) is to develop the necessary methods for the design and application of these strategies. For this purpose, the design procedures have been developed based on analytical and numerical analyses calibrated on the experimental results of "CONSTRAIN". The results provide the designers with robust strategies for the design of the proposed systems, and instructions for design in commonly used commercial programs for design of structures.

In the previous report "REPORT 1.1: Analytic model for dimensioning" [1] the CONSTRAIN experimental results are gathered, analysed in depth, compared and critically reviewed and a first approach to the definition and calibration of analytical-mechanical models capable to describe the experimental behaviour is presented.

This REPORT 1.2 presents the main features of the advanced numerical models developed to accurately simulate the behaviour of masonry elements strengthened with Composite Reinforced Mortar. The purpose of developing the detailed numerical models is to use them instead of expensive and time-consuming experimental tests on configurations that were not tested within CONSTRAIN. Moreover, these models will allow also a broader validation of more simplified predictive models for the seismic behaviour masonry structures strengthened with CRM (such as the equivalent frame method with lumped plasticity).

Two different finite element software were considered (ABAQUS and OOFEM) and this report provides a detailed description of the two simulation approaches applied for analysing the CONSTRAIN samples.

The ABAQUS models were developed primarily by the University of Ljubljana (UL FGG), while the OOFEM models were developed by the University of Trieste (DIA – UNITS). In this process,

the two partners began by sharing the same available experimental data, then worked independently, each autonomously defining its own procedures and analysis parameters. Once the simulations were completed, they combined and compared the results. Intentionally, some assumptions were not strictly enforced to be identical, in order to identify the impact of the uncertainty inherent in the two different approaches.

The report starts with a summary of the experimental evidences. Then, there are the two main sections of the report, one for each type modelling developed. For each section, the first part resumes the modelling approach, and the latter the numeric results, which include a comparison with the experimental CONSTRAIN tests. At the end, a final section provides a direct comparison and analyses of the results.

2. List of the experimental samples

The full-scale tests performed within CONSTRAIN project, that are modelled by the detailed numerical models are presented in Table 2.1. They consist of shear-compression tests on piers and shear-bending tests on spandrels. Rubble stone and solid brick masonry were considered, and different configurations of strengthening (unstrengthened, strengthened on one side and strengthened on both sides).

The labelling of samples presented in Table 2.1 and used throughout the report is as follows:

- P/S = Pier or Spandrel
- R2/B1/B2 = two leaf rubble/one leaf brick/two leaf brick
- U/R1/R2 = unstrengthened/strengthened on one side/strengthened on two sides

The main geometric characteristics of masonry pier and spandrel samples are illustrated in Fig. 2.1 and Fig. 2.2, respectively. All relevant dimensions are included, to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the configurations.

Detailed description of the experimental tests features and results can be found in [1].

Table 2.1: List of tests that are modelled by detailed numerical models

Type of test	Masonry type	Wall wythes	Label	Strengthening
In-plane tests on masonry piers	Stone	2	P-R2U	/
	Stone	2	P-R2R-1	CRM on one-side
	Stone	2	P-R2R-2	CRM on two-sides
	Solid brick	2	P-B2U	/
	Solid brick	2	P-B2R-1	CRM on one-side
	Solid brick	2	P-B2R-2	CRM on two-sides
	Solid brick	1	P-B1U	/
	Solid brick	1	P-B1R	CRM on one-side
In-plane tests on masonry spandrels	Stone	2	S-R2U-1	/
	Stone	2	S-R2R-1	CRM on one-side
	Stone	2	S-R2U-2	/
	Stone	2	S-R2R -2	CRM on two-sides
	Solid brick	2	S-B2U-1	/
	Solid brick	1	S-B2R-1	CRM on one-side
	Solid brick	1	S-B1U-1	/
	Solid brick	2	S-B1R-1	CRM on one-side

Fig. 2.1 Main geometric characteristics of the pier samples.

Fig. 2.2 Main geometric characteristics of the spandrel samples.

3. Numerical modelling with ABAQUS (by UL FGG)

ABAQUS Simulia [2] is a commercial software for modelling of structures using the finite element method. The program is suitable for modelling response of brittle or ductile materials, for static and dynamic analysis and is particularly known for its ability to model various contacts.

3.1. Modelling approach

The numerical models were developed to accurately capture the actual geometry and boundary conditions of the tested specimens, with certain separate considerations for piers and spandrels, as elaborated later. There are separate meshes for masonry, mortar coating and glass fibre mesh, and each material has its own nonlinear material model (see §3.2).

Both the masonry and the mortar coating were modelled as a continuum using 3D solid linear brick elements (C3D8R) with eight nodes and reduced integration, ensuring computational efficiency and stability in explicit dynamic simulations [2]. The glass fibre mesh, on the other hand, was represented using T3D2 elements, 2-node linear 3D truss elements, which was incorporated into the models as a separate component with lengths and positions taken from the tested pier and spandrels.

The masonry and mortar materials were characterized using the well-established Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) model, widely used for brittle materials such as masonry and concrete. The material parameters were carefully determined based on experimental tests on materials and further refined through calibration with experimental test results from piers and spandrels. The stress-strain relationships (shape of the curve) followed the modelling approach proposed by Stavridis and Shing [3].

Different material properties were assigned for each of the three masonry types in the study: two-leaf rubble stone, single-leaf brick, and double-leaf brick. Extensive numerical analyses confirmed that the material properties in tension played a crucial role in obtaining accurate wall response predictions. Consequently, the material model in tension was modified and adjusted to account for additional effects which were not explicitly considered, such as friction in cracks, interlocking of stones, coating debonding, and the influence of anchoring.

A similar approach was adopted for the mortar used in the strengthening method. The tensile material law was adjusted in parallel with the masonry parameters to ensure a consistent response. Particular attention was given to calibrating the composite interaction of the GFRP mesh and mortar, to adequately reproduce the behaviour observed in experimental tests.

The material model for GFRP mesh was modelled as a perfectly brittle elastic material using the Plastic model in ABAQUS. The rupture stress values were determined based on the experimentally observed rupture forces of each fibre type (weft of warped).

Explicit dynamic analyses were employed for the numerical simulations, given their well-known advantages in modelling brittle response, such as improved numerical stability and fewer convergence issues. The time increment varied depending on the type of simulation, with

minimum and maximum values set at 0.000001s and 0.001s, respectively. A dedicated parametric analysis was conducted to determine the optimal balance between computational efficiency and accuracy.

To further enhance computational speed, mass scaling was applied. The scaling factor was selected to achieve a target time increment of 0.001 s for pilot building analyses and between 0.0001 s and 0.00008 s for other simulations. Additional analyses confirmed that mass scaling had a negligible influence on accuracy of the results. Simulations performed with and without mass scaling produced nearly identical results, as illustrated in Fig. 3.1.

Fig. 3.1 Comparison of typical pushover curves for models with and without mass scaling.

3.2. Material models

- Stone masonry

Material properties of stone masonry in compression were based on two compression tests on stone masonry and tests on masonry piers and spandrels (see CONSTRAN report for details [4]). The pre-peak stress strain constitutive model was taken as the average of two compression tests, as shown in Fig. 3.2a. Elastic modulus amounted to 4500 MPa and peak compressive strength to $f_c = 2.5$ MPa.

The post-peak part of the constitutive model for compression is characterized by a gradual reduction towards the residual strength, which is 20% of the compressive strength ($r_c = 0.2 f_c$). The complete constitutive law for stone masonry in compression is shown in Fig. 3.2b.

The constitutive model for tension was defined as a stress-strain curve according to the recommendations of Stavridis and Shing [3]. As mentioned in the previous Section, this part of the material response had the greatest influence on the results and was modified to account for phenomena not explicitly included in the model. Therefore, a high residual tensile strength ($r_t = 0.4 f_t$) was assumed, with a large deformation of 2.5 % at final failure in tension in order to match the ductility of spandrel samples. Tensile strength was 0.21 MPa (about 8 % of

compressive strength of stone masonry). The stress-strain relationship under tension for the stone masonry is shown in Fig. 3.3.

Fig. 3.2 Stress-strain curve for stone masonry in compression: (a) pre-peak response and comparison with experiment and (b) post-peak response.

Fig. 3.3 Stress-strain curve for stone masonry in tension: (a) the initial response and (b) complete response.

- Single leaf brick masonry

Material properties of single-leaf brick masonry in compression were based on two compression tests, and tests on masonry piers and spandrels (see CONSTRAIN report [3] for details). The pre-peak stress strain constitutive model was assumed based on a compression test, as shown in Fig. 3.4. Elastic modulus amounted to 2341 MPa and peak compressive strength to $f_c = 6.7$ MPa.

The post-peak part of the constitutive model for compression is characterized by a gradual reduction towards the residual strength, which is 20% of the compressive strength ($r_c = 0.2 f_c$). The complete constitutive law for single-leaf brick masonry in compression is shown in Fig. 3.4.

The constitutive model for tension was defined as a stress-strain curve, similar to that for stone masonry, based on the work of Stavridis and Shing [3]. This part of the material curve had the greatest influence on the results, as stated in the previous Section. The newly adjusted model incorporates phenomena that were not explicitly modelled in the original version. Therefore, a

high residual tensile strength ($r_t = 0.66 f_t$) was assumed, with a large deformation of 2.5 % at final failure in tension, again for accounting spandrel's ductility. Tensile strength of single-leaf brick masonry was set to 0.23 MPa. The stress-strain relationship under tension for the single-leaf brick masonry is shown in Fig. 3.5.

Fig. 3.4 Stress-strain curve for single-leaf brick masonry in compression.

Fig. 3.5 Stress-strain curve for single-leaf brick masonry in tension: (a) initial response and (b) complete response.

- Double leaf brick masonry

Material properties of double-leaf brick masonry in compression were based on two compression tests on masonry and tests on masonry piers and spandrels (see CONSTRAIN report [4] for details). The pre-peak stress strain constitutive model was determined based on a compression test, and is shown in Fig. 3.6. Elastic modulus amounted to 2200 MPa and peak compressive strength to $f_c = 6.4$ MPa.

The post-peak part of the constitutive model for compression was characterised by gradual reduction towards the residual strength, which amounted to 20% of compressive strength ($r_c = 0.2 f_c$). The complete constitutive law for double-leaf brick masonry in compression is shown in Fig. 3.6.

The constitutive model for tension was defined as a stress-strain curve, following the approach of Stavridis and Shing [3]. As highlighted in previous sections, the stress-strain curve in tension had the most significant influence on the results and was adjusted to account for phenomena

not explicitly included in the original model. It should be noted that the high residual tensile strength ($r_t = 0.84 f_t$) was assumed with a large deformation of 1.13 % at final failure in tension with respect to spandrel's ductility. Tensile strength of the double-leaf brick masonry was set to 0.14 MPa. The stress-strain relationship under tension for the double-leaf brick masonry is shown in Fig. 3.7.

Fig. 3.6 Stress-strain curve for double-leaf brick masonry in compression.

Fig. 3.7 Stress-strain curve for double-leaf brick masonry in tension: (a) initial response and (b) complete response.

- Mortar coating

The stress-strain formulation for mortar coating in compression was the same as for stone and brick masonry. Elastic modulus was 9000 MPa, as specified in technical datasheet, and the compressive strength f_c was 30.1 MPa. Residual strength was set to 0 MPa. The graph of the material model for mortar coating is shown in Fig. 3.8.

The tensile portion of the constitutive model (Fig. 3.9) was determined in the same manner as for stone masonry, with the residual tensile strength set to 30 % of the tensile strength ($r_c = 0.3 f_c$). Both the peak tensile and residual strengths were calibrated based on experimental results. The final residual tensile strength was set to 0 MPa to reflect the brittle failure of the mortar after the rupture of the GFRP, which occurred at a strain of 2.3 %.

Fig. 3.8 Stress-strain curve for mortar coating in compression.

Fig. 3.9 Stress-strain curve for mortar coating in tension: (a) initial response and (b) complete response.

- GFRP mesh

The constitutive material model for the glass fibres was derived from the results of axial tensile tests. The values for elastic modulus are taken from the technical datasheet, and equal to 36400 MPa and 31443 MPa for weft and warped yarns, respectively. The mesh has different properties for weft and warped directions, as presented in Fig. 3.10.

Fig. 3.10 Tensile and compressive stress-strain curves for GFRP mesh.

- Concrete

The concrete material used for modelling the foundations and top beam was treated as an ideally elastic material in ABAQUS software, with an elastic modulus of 40000 MPa.

3.3. In-plane behaviour of piers

3.3.1. *Geometry, boundary conditions and loads*

The models consist of masonry wall (stone or brick) and two concrete beams, one at the top and one at the bottom, as seen in Fig. 3.11. GFRP mesh is embedded inside the mortar coating. Additionally, two steel beams are included as part of the testing apparatus, positioned above and below the concrete beams. In the numerical model, contact springs were placed between the steel and concrete elements to reproduce the displacements that were measured at those locations.

Fig. 3.11 ABAQUS models for piers: unstrengthened U (a), strengthened on one side R1 (b) and both sides R2 (c).

The boundary conditions are illustrated in Fig. 3.12. The bottom steel beam is fixed to the laboratory floor, restricting both horizontal and vertical movements as well as rotation, in accordance with the experimental setup. The top steel beam is free to move horizontally and vertically while its rotations remain constrained, ensuring realistic replication of experimental conditions.

Between the steel and concrete beams, springs were used as connectors to model the uplift observed at the heel during experiments. A connector stiffness of 1.875 N/mm/mm² was applied consistently across all tests to capture this behaviour. These connectors permitted movement only in the vertical direction, while translations in the other two directions were restricted using slot-type connectors available in ABAQUS [2].

At the start of the numerical simulation, a constant vertical pressure of 0.5 MPa was applied to the top steel beam surface, with the self-weight of the material contributing to the total vertical load (Fig. 3.12). This vertical load remained constant throughout the simulation, which is consistent with the experimental conditions. Following the application of the vertical load, a monotonic horizontal displacement was introduced at the top steel beam, pushing from left to right (Fig. 3.13).

As mentioned at the beginning, the analyses were of the explicit dynamic type. The duration of each analysis was specified individually for each experiment, ensuring a balance between computational efficiency and numerical accuracy by maintaining a reasonable simulation time.

Fig. 3.12 Boundary conditions and applied load in the numerical models.

Fig. 3.13 Load amplitudes.

Regarding the contact definition, the concrete beam was constrained to the masonry in the tangential direction, assuming infinite friction, while allowing separation in the normal direction to accommodate tensile opening. All other contacts were fully tied.

3.3.2. Numerical results and comparisons

- Pier P-R2-U

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of unstrengthened stone masonry pier and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation on the FE model in the ABAQUS software are presented in Fig. 3.14a. The deformed configuration of unstrengthened stone masonry pier P-R2U is shown in Fig. 3.14b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.15. Finally, the uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.16.

Fig. 3.14 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-R2-U (a) and deformed configuration of the model (b).

Fig. 3.15 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (plastic strain - PE) (a) and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.16 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

- Pier P-R2-R1

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of stone masonry pier P-R2-R1 and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.17a. The deformed configurations of the mortar coating, and the stone masonry under the mortar are shown in 3.19b-c. The comparison of the damage predicted by numerical simulation and damage pattern observed in the experiment are shown in Fig. 3.18. Fig. 3.19 shows the damage in the GFRP mesh in terms of rupture of fibres. The uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.20.

Fig. 3.17 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-R2-R1 (a) and deformed configuration, with view of the mortar coating (b) and of the stone masonry (b). Deformation scale is 10.

Fig. 3.18 Elastic strains – view of mortar (a) and stone masonry under the mortar (b) and experiment (c).

Fig. 3.19 Elastic strain in GFRP. Red zones indicate ruptured fibres.

Fig. 3.20 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

- Pier P-R2-R2

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of stone masonry pier P-R2-R2 and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.21. The deformed configurations of the mortar coating, and the stone masonry under the mortar are also shown in Fig. 3.21. The comparison of the damage predicted by numerical simulation and damage pattern observed in the experiment are shown in Fig. 3.22. The damage predicted in the GFRP mesh is shown in Fig. 3.23. Finally, the uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.24.

Fig. 3.21 (Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-R2-R2 (a) and deformed configuration of the model (b)).

Fig. 3.22 Elastic strains – view of mortar (a), masonry under the mortar (b) and experiment (c).

Fig. 3.23 Elastic strain in GFRP. Red zones indicate ruptured fibres.

Fig. 3.24 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

- Pier P-B1-U

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of unstrengthened single-leaf brick masonry pier and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation in the ABAQUS software are presented in Fig. 3.25a. The deformed configuration of unstrengthened brick masonry pier P-B1U is shown in Fig. 3.25b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.26. Finally, the uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.27.

Fig. 3.25 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-B1-U (a) and deformed configuration of the model (b).

Fig. 3.26 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (plastic strain - PE), (a) and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.27 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

- Pier P-B1-R1

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of a single-leaf brick masonry pier strengthened on one side P-B1-R1 and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.28a. The deformed configurations of the mortar coating, and the brick masonry under the mortar are shown in Fig. 3.28b-c. The comparison of the damage predicted by numerical simulation and damage pattern observed in the experiment are shown in Fig. 3.29. Fig. 3.30 shows the damage in the GFRP mesh in terms of rupture of fibres. The uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.31.

Fig. 3.28 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-B1-R1 (a) and deformed configuration: view of the mortar coating (b) and of the masonry (c). Deformation scale is 10.

Fig. 3.29 Plastic strains – view of mortar (a), masonry under the mortar (b) and experiment (c).

Fig. 3.30 Elastic strain in GFRP. Red zones indicate ruptured fibres.

Fig. 3.31 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

- Pier P-B2-U

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of unstrengthened double-leaf brick masonry pier and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation in the ABAQUS software are presented in Fig. 3.32a. The deformed configuration of unstrengthened brick masonry pier P-B2U is shown in Fig. 3.32b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.33. Finally, the uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.34.

Fig. 3.32 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-B2-U (a) and deformed configuration of the model (b).

Fig. 3.33 Damage (plastic strain) (a) and damage during experiment (b).

Fig. 3.34 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

- Pier P-B2-R1

The capacity curve (V_p-d_p) of single double leaf brick masonry pier strengthened on one side (P-B2-R1) is shown in Fig. 3.35a. Deformed configurations of the pier, and the masonry below the pier are shown in Fig. 3.35b-c. Damage in mortar and masonry, and comparison of the damage to the experiment are shown in Fig. 3.36. Fig. 3.37 shows the damage in the GFRP mesh. Finally, the uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.38.

Fig. 3.35 Push Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-B2-R1 (a) and deformed configuration: view of the mortar coating (b) and of the masonry (c). Deformation scale is 10.

Fig. 3.36 Plastic strains - view of mortar (a), masonry under the mortar (b) and experiment (c).

Fig. 3.37 GFRP elastic strain. Red zones show ruptured fibres.

Fig. 3.38 Uplift at the heel, compression at the toe and comparison with the experiment.

- Pier P-B2-R2

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of a double-leaf brick masonry pier strengthened on both sides P-B2-R2 and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.39a. The deformed configuration of brick masonry pier P-B2-R2 is shown in Fig. 3.39b. The comparison of the damage predicted by numerical simulation and damage pattern observed in the experiment are shown in Fig. 3.40. Fig. 3.41 shows the damage in the GFRP mesh in terms of rupture of fibres. The uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.42.

Fig. 3.39 (a) Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-B2-R2; (b) Deformed configuration of the model.

Fig. 3.40 Elastic strains - view of mortar (a), masonry under the mortar (b) and experiment (c).

Fig. 3.41 Elastic strain in GFRP. Red zones indicate ruptured fibres.

Fig. 3.42 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

3.4. In-plane behaviour of spandrels

3.4.1. *Geometry, boundary conditions and loads*

The models comprise of masonry wall (stone or brick) and four concrete beams, two at the top and two at the bottom, as seen in Fig. 3.43. GFRP mesh is embedded inside the mortar coating, and applied on one or both sides the masonry.

Fig. 3.43 The FEM mesh in ABAQUS models of spandrels.

The boundary conditions are illustrated in Fig. 3.44. Initially, the concrete beam on the bottom left could only rotate around its center, while the concrete beam on the bottom right could rotate around its center and slide horizontally.

Fig. 3.44 Boundary conditions and applied load in the models.

A constant vertical pressure of 0.4 MPa was applied to the top concrete beam surfaces. This pressure of 0.4 MPa is the sum of the 0.33 MPa vertical pressure during the experiment and the total gravity load force divided by the top beam surface area (Fig. 3.44). This vertical load remained constant throughout the simulation, which is consistent with the experimental conditions.

Following the application of the vertical load, shear and bending loads were applied through displacements at the inner edges of the bottom concrete beams, as seen in Fig. 3.44. The displacements on the left and right were equal but in opposite directions. The loading was applied monotonically, resulting in clockwise rotations of the piers. The imposed displacement was applied after the vertical load (Fig. 3.45).

As previously stated, the analyses were of the explicit dynamic type. The duration of analysis was specified individually for each experiment in order to have minimal but long enough time duration for optimal time efficiency – numerical accuracy of our model.

Fig. 3.45 Load amplitudes.

Concrete beam is tied to masonry (stone or brick) in tangential direction to achieve infinite friction but allows separation in normal direction (tensile opening).

Regarding the interaction between wooden lintel and stone masonry is defined as friction contact with friction coefficient 0.1 that allows separation (tension induced opening). ON the other hand, interaction between brick arch lintel and brick masonry is defined as friction contact with friction coefficient 0.5 that allows separation (tension induced opening).

All other contacts were tied.

3.4.2. Numerical results and comparisons

- Spandrel S-R2-U

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of unstrengthened stone masonry spandrel and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation in the ABAQUS software are presented in Fig. 3.46a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of unstrengthened stone masonry spandrel S-R2U is shown in Fig. 3.46b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.47. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.48. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be reproduced by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.46 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-R2-U (a) and deformed configuration of unstrengthened stone masonry spandrel (b).

Fig. 3.47 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (logarithmic strain - LE), (a). Damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.48 Horizontal movement of the right support.

- Spandrel S-R2-R1

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of stone masonry spandrel strengthened on one side and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.49a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of stone masonry spandrel S-R2-R1 is shown in Fig. 3.49b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.50. The strain and locations of fracture of GFRP fibres are shown in Fig. 3.51. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.52. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be reproduced by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.49 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-R2-R1 (a) and deformed configuration of stone masonry spandrel strengthened on one side (b)

(c)

Fig. 3.50 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (logarithmic strain - LE) in mortar coating (a) and in the masonry (b), and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.51 GFRP strains. Fibres in red zones have ruptured.

Fig. 3.52 Horizontal movement of the right support.

- Spandrel S-R2-R2

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of stone masonry spandrel strengthened on both sides and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.53a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of the spandrel model is shown in Fig. 3.53b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.54. The strain and fracture locations of the GFRP fibres are shown in Fig. 3.55. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.56. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be replicated by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.53 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-R2-R2 (a) and deformed configuration of stone masonry spandrel strengthened on both sides (b).

(c)

Fig. 3.54 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (logarithmic strain - LE) in mortar coating (a) and in the masonry (b), and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.55 GFRP strains. Fibres in red zones have ruptured.

Fig. 3.56 Horizontal movement of the right support.

- Spandrel S-B1-U

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of unstrengthened single-leaf brick masonry spandrel and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation in the ABAQUS software are presented in Fig. 3.57a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of brick masonry spandrel S-B1U is shown in Fig. 3.57b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.58. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.59. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be reproduced by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.57 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-B1-U (a) and deformed configuration of unstrengthened single-leaf brick masonry spandrel (b)

Fig. 3.58 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (plastic strain - PE), (a) and damage pattern observed during the experiment, right (b).

Fig. 3.59 Horizontal movement of the right support.

- Spandrel S-B1-R1

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of single-leaf brick masonry spandrel strengthened on one side and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.60a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of brick masonry spandrel S-B1-R1 is shown in Fig. 3.60b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.61. The strain and locations of fracture of GFRP fibres are shown in Fig. 3.62. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.63. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be replicated by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.60 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-B1-R1 (a) and deformed configuration of single-leaf brick masonry spandrel strengthened on one side (b).

Fig. 3.61 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation in mortar coating (plastic strain - PE), (a) and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.62 GFRP strains. Fibres in red zones have ruptured.

Fig. 3.63 Horizontal movement of the right support.

- Spandrel S-B2U

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of unstrengthened double-leaf brick masonry spandrel and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation in the ABAQUS software are presented in Fig. 3.64a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of brick masonry spandrel S-B2U is shown in Fig. 3.64b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.65. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.66. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be replicated by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.64 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-B2U (a) and deformed configuration of unstrengthened double-leaf brick masonry spandrel (b).

Fig. 3.65 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (plastic strain - PE), (a) and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b)

Fig. 3.66 Horizontal movement of the right support.

- Spandrel S-B2-R1

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of double-leaf brick masonry spandrel strengthened on one side and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.67a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of brick masonry spandrel S-B2-R1 is shown in Fig. 3.67b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.68. The strain and locations of fracture of GFRP fibres are shown in Fig. 3.69. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.70. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be replicated by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.67 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-B2-R1 (a) and deformed configuration of double-leaf masonry spandrel strengthened on one side (b)

(c)

Fig. 3.68 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (logarithmic strain - LE) in mortar coating (a) and in the masonry (b), and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.69 GFRP strains. Fibres in red zones have ruptured.

Fig. 3.70 Horizontal movement of the right support.

4. Numerical modelling with OOFEM (by DIA – UNITS)

OOFEM [5] is a free, open-source code for finite element modelling (FEM), featuring an object-oriented architecture for addressing mechanical, transport, and fluid mechanics problems [6]-[7]. It is released under the GNU Lesser General Public License (LGPL v2.1) and offers a modular and extensible environment. The current version is OOFEM 2.5 [8]. For detailed information on the types of elements and materials used in simulations, refer to the OOFEM manuals section available online.

4.1. Modelling approach

The models are composed by using 20-node brick elements ("QSpace" OOFEM element type) with dimensions of $167 \times 167 \times T$ mm³, where T represents the overall wall thickness. The mesh size is selected to maintain an aspect ratio (the ratio between the largest and smallest characteristic dimension) between 1.5 and 3 (for numeric reliability), considering typical thickness range in existing masonry walls and providing good balance between representation accuracy and numeric convergence facilitation.

The elements feature layered cross sections ("LayeredCS" OOFEM cross section type), consisting of different layers arranged along the sample thickness, so to represent the original masonry, the fiber-based reinforcement, and the mortar coating (Fig. 4.1). The simplified hypotheses of perfectly bonded layers and planar cross sections are assumed. Position of mid surface is determined by its distance from bottom of cross section (normal and momentum forces are then computed with regard to its position, by default it is located at average thickness position). The number of integration points per layer can be specified (it is possible to set up different number of integration points per individual layer). The Gauss integration rule is used for setting up integration points in each layer. Specifically, 6 integration points are set for the masonry layer, 3 for the mortar coating, and 1 for the GFRP layer.

Fig. 4.1 Schematization of 20-nodes multi-layer elements used in the OOFEM models.

Nonlinear static analyses under displacement control, accounting for material nonlinearities, are performed by using the Newton-Raphson solver (relative displacement and force convergence norms set to $3 \cdot 10^{-3}$). For simplified assumption, all the materials are considered as homogeneous and isotropic, with properties set on the basis of from experimental data.

4.2. Material models

For the masonry, a concrete-damage plasticity material model is used ("CdpM2" OOFEM material type) to account for both cracking in tension and crushing in compression. The mechanical parameters are resumed in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Main numerical parameters adopted for the masonry layer (for unspecified parameters, the OOFEM default values are used [5]).

Masonry layer	Type R2	Type B2	Type B1	
OOFEM material type	CdpM2	CdpM2	CdpM2	
Secant Young's modulus E	1.07 GPa	1.34 GPa	1.64 GPa	
Initial Young's modulus E_{init}	3.22 GPa	4.00 GPa	4.92 GPa	
Poisson modulus ν	0.45	0.45	0.45	
Self-weight γ	21.0 kN/m ³	18 kN/m ³	18 kN/m ³	
Comp. strength f_c	2.48 MPa	2.98 MPa	3.84 MPa	
Tensile strength f_t	0.085* MPa	0.102**MPa	0.162 MPa	
Dilation ψ	40°	40°	40°	
Softening law	Linear	Linear	Linear	
Hardening parameters	b_h	0.022	0.015	0.015
	h_p	0.0	0.0	0.0
	k_{init}	0.15	0.15	0.15
Softening parameters	w_f/h	0.004	0.004	0.004
	a_{soft}	5.0	8.0	8.0

Tensile behavior

Compressive behavior

* reduced value, to account for the relevant interlocking effect in rubble stone masonry

** or 0.102×1.3 for masonry provided with transversal connectors and diatons, coherently to [1]

It is observed that the strength and stiffness parameters (f_t , f_c , E) are generally those already considered in the analytic study performed in the PRO-SIS project (with $f_t = 1.5 \tau_0$) [1]. In exception, a reduced value of equivalent tensile strength was considered for masonry type R2 ($\sim 0.8 f_t$), coherently with the numerical study carried out by Brignola et al. [10]. In fact, in that study it was observed that in rubble stone masonry a relevant redistribution of the stresses due to the interlocking effect occurs in the specimen (which is almost negligible in regular, solid brick masonry), resulting in a further appreciable increase of the diagonal cracking load after the occurrence of the first cracking.

So that, since the values of f_t were calculated in [1] from the unstrengthened panel resistance, a reduction is deemed necessary for masonry R2, to correctly detect the first cracking.

For all masonry types, the stress-strain uniaxial tensile law is linear elastic till reaching f_t ; the resistance is initially maintained constant and, then, a linear decay occurs. For compression, the stress-strain uniaxial law is linear elastic till achieving k_{init} times the strength (k_{init} set to 0.15), then it prosecutes with a parabolic trend, accounting for a progressive stiffness degradation: the initial value of Young's modulus E_{init} is set equal to 3 times the mean, secant one E ; then an exponential law decay is considered.

The masonry constitutive laws under uniaxial compressive and tensile stresses are represented in Fig. 4.2. The softening parameters are calibrated so to fit the results of the CONSTRAIN in-plane cyclic tests on unstrengthened masonry piers.

It is important to note that, due to the assumption of a homogeneous isotropic material, the masonry behavior is considered uniform in all directions, irrespective of the orientation relative to the bed joints. While this simplified assumption may not precisely simulate the behavior of unreinforced masonry, it is deemed an acceptable approximation for the model purpose, focused on CRM-strengthened reinforced masonry.

Fig. 4.2 Masonry uniaxial constitutive laws in (a) compression and (b) tension.

To the uniform layer representing the Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) mesh, a unitary thickness is assigned. The material parameters are based on experimental outcomes from tensile tests on GFRP yarns and are scaled over the uniform layer. For this simplification, the average resistance of the GFRP yarns in the two mesh directions is considered. The main parameters are resumed in Table 4.2; it is observed that the stiffness and peak strain parameters (E , ϵ_0) are coherent to those already considered in the analytic study performed in the PRO-SIS project [1].

The isotropic damage model for tensile failure is assigned to the layer ("*ldm1*" OOFEM material type), so the material to be linear elastic in tension up to peak tensile stress and then performing a linear stress decay, with slope set so to account for the progressive breakage of concurrently stressed yarns (the so called "group effect"). The compressive resistance is neglected. Moreover, the contribution of the layer to the shear stiffness of the wall is neglected by setting a low Poisson's ratio.

Table 4.2 Main numerical parameters adopted for the GFRP layer (for unspecified parameters, the OOFEM default values are used [5]).

GFRP layer	
OOFEM material type	<i>ldm1</i>
Young's modulus E	3.81 GPa
Poisson modulus ν	0.01
Comp. strength f_c	0
OOFEM Equiv. strain type	modified Mises
Peak strain ϵ_0	1.8%
Damage law	linear
Ultimate strain ϵ_u	6.0%

For the mortar of the coating layer (30 mm thick), a concrete-damage plasticity material model is used ("Cdpm2" OOFEM material type); the main parameters are resumed in Table 4.3. It is observed that, due to the smeared-crack approach of the multi-layer model, the fracture energy necessitates to be fictitiously increased so to account for the tension stiffening effect between cracks. This adjustment allows the combined effect of the plaster and GFRP layers to macroscopically reproduce the typical trilinear tensile behaviour of the Composite Reinforced Mortar (CRM) material.

To clarify, in Fig. 4.3, it is reported the comparison between the experimental behaviour of CRM coupons subjected to direct tensile tests [9] and the numeric results obtained from the simulation, according to the multi-layer modelling (GFRP and mortar layer only). Clearly, the numeric model, being smear-cracked, do not allow the detection of the single cracks, nor the respective jagged stress-strain curve characterizing the post-cracking stage, but catches with satisfying approximation the typical trilinear behaviour of CRM, as well as the spreading of plasticization over the whole coupon length. Note also that the mortar tensile strength in the model is properly reduced, to fit adequately the mean behaviour of the post-cracking stage. Also the peak strain of the GFRP layer is properly reduced in respect the values considered in [1] (from 2% to 1.8%), so that the composite material "mortar coating + GFRP" fails in tension at the attainment of the actual GFRP peak stress.

For the compressive strength of the mortar, a very low, fictitious value was considered in the numeric simulations. In fact, experimental compression test on CRM strengthened masonry provided resistance values just slightly higher than of plain masonry, due to the debonding of the mortar coating. Since in the simplified, multi-layer numeric model this debonding is not considered (perfect bond between layers is assumed), a negligible value of mortar compressive strength was set.

Table 4.3 Main numerical parameters adopted for the mortar coating layer (for unspecified parameters, the OOFEM default values are used [5]).

Mortar layer	
OOFEM material type	<i>Cdpm2</i>
Young modulus E	14.4 GPa
Poisson modulus n	0.25
Self-weight γ	20 kN/m ³
Comp. strength f_c	0.85 MPa
Tensile strength f_t	0.85 MPa
Dilation ψ	40°
Softening law	Bilinear
Hardening parameters b_h	0.002
h_p	0.0
Softening parameters w_f/h	0.035
a_{soft}	4
f_{t1}	0.45
w_{f1}/h	0.0045

Tensile behavior

Compressive behavior

Fig. 4.3 Schematization of 20-nodes multi-layer elements used in the OOFEM models.

4.3. In-plane behaviour of piers

4.3.1. *Geometry, boundary conditions and loads*

The numerical model to reproduce the CONSTRAIN tests carried out on masonry piers samples, subjected to in-plane cyclic loading is schematized in Fig. 4.4: red colour represents the steel parts of the testing apparatus, blue colour the RC beams, grey the masonry sample.

The solid elements of the lower row are fixed at the base, while the steel and the RC beams (below and above the masonry sample) are linked by means of vertical elastic springs aimed at stimulating the slight but not negligible vertical displacements actually monitored experimentally in those areas (already discussed in [1]). Differently, a perfect bond was assumed between the masonry pier and the RC beams. It is observed that, when simulating the CRM strengthened masonry samples, the multi-layer approach is assumed also for the RC beams, since in the experimental sample the CRM application prosecuted also over such beams.

To avoid rotations of the upper steel beam (coherently with the experimental setup), a master node is selected at the location of the horizontal actuator, and all other nodes at that height are constrained to have the same translations. To simply model connectors and diatones, axial rigid links were used to connect nodes on opposite faces of the wall, where the anchors were located.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is distributed across the top of the upper steel beam and then kept constant. Subsequently, a horizontal, in-plane load is applied at the actuator's height and varied to increase step-by-step the horizontal displacement of the control point (at the top of the pier sample).

Fig. 4.4 The OOFEM numeric model for the CONSTRAIN in-plane tests on piers

4.3.2. Numerical results and comparisons

The main numerical results are summarized with thick lines in the V_p - d_p graphs of Fig. 4.5, in comparison with the thin lines of the experiments. The applied horizontal load V_p (shear force) is plotted as function of the horizontal displacement of the top RC beam d_p .

Fig. 4.5 Numeric analyses of the CONSTRAIN in-plane tests on masonry piers: capacity curves, in comparison with the experimental results.

More detailed numerical-experimental comparisons are plotted in Fig. 4.6-Fig. 4.13:

- the V_p - d_p graphs;
- the V_p - d_{Vtot} graphs, being d_{Vtot} the global vertical displacements between the upper steel beam and the laboratory floor (positive displacements conventionally refer to elongations);
- the principal tensile strains evidencing the damage patterns at 20% reduction of peak load (just the sample and RC beam are represented), in comparison with the crack pattern surveyed at the back side of the experimental samples by means of a Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system.

Considering the coarseness of the numerical model, all the numerical curves generally show good agreement with the envelope of the cyclic experimental ones.

Also, the damage patterns well correspond with the failure modes observed in the CONSTRAIN experiments. Specifically, the unstrengthened samples fail due to diagonal cracking (with high tensile strains along the diagonal), while the strengthened samples exhibit mixed damage patterns, consistently with experimental findings. In particular, high tensile strains at opposite top-bottom extremities (damage related to the in-plane bending mechanism) are also observed.

For samples S-R2R-1 and S-B2R-1, strengthened on one side only, diagonal cracking remains the dominant failure mode, whereas samples strengthened on both sides and sample S-B1R-1 exhibit a combination of diagonal cracking and bending failure modes.

- Pier P-R2U

Fig. 4.6 Pier sample P-R2U: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-R2R-1

Fig. 4.7 Pier sample P-R2R-1: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-R2R-2

Fig. 4.8 Pier sample P-R2R-2: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-B2U

Fig. 4.9 Pier sample P-B2U: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-B2R-1

Fig. 4.10 Pier sample P-B2R-1: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-B2R-2

Fig. 4.11 Pier sample P-B2R-2: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-B1U

Fig. 4.12 Pier sample P-B1U: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-B1R-1

Fig. 4.13 Pier sample P-B1R-1: numerical – experimental comparisons.

4.4. In-plane behaviour of spandrels

4.4.1. *Geometry, boundary conditions and loads*

The numerical model to reproduce the CONSTRAIN tests carried out on masonry spandrel samples, subjected to in-plane cyclic loading is schematized in Fig. 4.14: red colour represents the steel parts of the testing apparatus, blue colour the RC beams, grey the masonry sample, green the lintel or jack arch. To simply reproduce connectors and diatones, axial rigid links are introduced to join the nodes at the opposite wall faces, in correspondance of the anchors. The nodes in correspondance of the left lever fulcrum are pinned, while in those at the right lever fulcrum the horizontal translation is free.

To represent, in a very simplified way, the extreme weakness emerged in the contact area between the lintel (or the jack arch) and the overlaying masonry, a negligible Young modulus was assigned to the masonry layer of the mesh elements just above the lintel/jack arch (detected with orange contour in Fig. 4.14).

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the self-weights are applied and the axial pre-compression on the piers is introduced by means of four vertical nodal forces at top; subsequently, the vertical displacement at the external ends of the two lever beams is incremented monotonically, with same magnitude but opposite directions.

Fig. 4.14 The OOFEM numeric model for the CONSTRAIN in-plane tests on spandrels.

4.4.2. Numerical results and comparisons

The numerical V_S - d_S capacity curves are reported with thick lines in Fig. 4.15 in comparison with the thin lines of the experiments.

The shear load V_S is obtained from the vertical translation equilibrium of the external vertical forces acting on the left half (as well as right half) of the sample. The spandrel distortion d_S is calculated by using Eq. (4.1):

$$d_S = (\delta_{V,r} - \delta_{V,l}) \cdot \left(\frac{b_S}{2} + \frac{b_P}{2} \right) / \left(\frac{b_P}{2} \right) \quad (4.1)$$

where b_S and b_P are the spandrel and the pier widths, respectively and δ_V the vertical displacements in correspondance on the inner corners of the two masonry columns (right - r , and left - l).

Fig. 4.15 Summary of the numerical analyses of the CONSTRAN in-plane tests on masonry spandrels: capacity curves, in comparison with the experimental results.

Two different numerical curves are plotted for S-R2R-2: a first simulation (dashed line) was carried out accordingly to the default load pattern of the experimental tests (i.e. the same rotation of the the two piers). A further simulation (solid lines) was performed by applying on the left pier half the rotation compared to right pier, in order to fictitiously replicate the actual boundary conditions observed in this sample during the experimental test (see [1] for further experimental details). This latter configuration reproduced more accurately the experimental outcomes; however, the former should be considered for consistent comparisons e.g. with S-R1R-1.

Two different numerical curves are plotted also for S-B2R-1 and S-B1R-1: in addition to the standard simulation (solid lines), a further simulation (dashed lines) was carried out by considering reducing values of the masonry material parameters for the spandrel. In fact, since it was observed that the standard simulations tended to overestimate the strength of these samples, it was realistically hypothesized that the pre-existing damage of the masonry (related to the previous test on the unreinforced configuration [1]) might have compromised its characteristics. The crack sealing intervention carried out before the application of the reinforcement likely only partially restored the original parameters. In the simulations, the Young's modulus, the compressive and tensile strengths, and the softening parameter wf/h reported in Table 4.1 were divided by 3. It is observed that this modification was not applied to the retrofitted samples made of stone masonry and having a timber lintel, which are likely less affected by pre-existing damage (as emerged from the pseudo-ductile behavior of S-R2U-1/2, compared to the brittle behavior exhibited experimentally by S-B2U and S-B1U).

More detailed numerical-experimental comparisons are plotted in Fig. 4.16-Fig. 4.13:

- the V_S-d_S graphs;
- the V_P-d_{Ht} graphs, being d_H the horizontal sliding of the right support;
- the $V_P-\epsilon_{top}$ and $V_P-\epsilon_{bot}$ graphs, being ϵ_{top} and ϵ_{bot} the equivalent horizontal strains at the top and the bottom of the spandrels, respectively
- the $V_P-\epsilon_{d1}$ and $V_P-\epsilon_{d2}$ graphs, being ϵ_{d1} and ϵ_{d2} the equivalent strains across the spandrels diagonals.
- the principal tensile strains evidencing the damage patterns at 20% reduction of peak load (just the spandrel area is represented), in comparison with the crack pattern surveyed at the front side of the experimental samples by means of a Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system.

It is observed that two different analyses were performed for the unstrengthened configurations: one simulating the unbounded condition of the lintel/jack arch with the overlying masonry (dashed line curves), the other (solid line curves) assuming perfect bond (i.e. no modifications in masonry properties in the above lintel/jack arch area).

For sample S-R2U, the perfect bond assumption was found to be the most consistent with the experimental behavior; conversely, for samples S-B2U and S-B1U, the unbounded condition fits better.

Considering the coarseness of the model, the numerical curves show good agreement with the envelope of the cyclic experimental ones. Also, the damage patterns generally reflect the failure modes observed in the CONSTRAIN experiments.

The failure of S-R2U is dominated by the in-plane bending mechanism. In S-B2U and S-B1U, also the activation of the diagonal cracking mechanism emerged, but the failure is induced by bending. For S-B2U, this is in contrast with the experiment, where diagonal cracking failure occurred.

The bending mechanism prevailed in the one-side retrofitted samples, even though in combination with an advanced diagonal cracking mechanism. Unsymmetrical bending failure occurred in S-R2R-2, under “modified boundary” conditions.

The pre-damage of the masonry seems to have a not negligible influence on the reinforced brick samples, consistently with the brittle behavior exhibited by the unreinforced configurations. Differently, the impact appears to be less pronounced in the stone samples, accordingly with the more ductile behavior observed in the unreinforced configurations.

- Spandrel S-R2U-1

Fig. 4.16 Spandrel sample S-R2U-1: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-R2U-2

Fig. 4.17 Spandrel sample S-R2U-2: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-R2R-1

Fig. 4.18 Spandrel sample S-R2R-1: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-R2R-1

Fig. 4.19 Spandrel sample S-R2R-2: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-B2U

Fig. 4.20 Spandrel sample S-B2U: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-B2R-1

Fig. 4.21 Spandrel sample S-B2R-1: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-B1U

Fig. 4.22 Spandrel sample S-B1U: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-B1R-1

Fig. 4.23 Spandrel sample S-B1R-1: numerical – experimental comparisons

5. Direct comparisons and remarks

The results from the ABAQUS and OOFEM numerical simulations are compared and the differences analysed.

5.1. In-plane behaviour of piers

- Pier P-R2U

Fig. 5.1 Direct comparison for pier sample P-R2U.

Both models capture diagonal shear damage and failure adequately. ABAQUS model shows steeper drop of pushover curve immediately after maximum resistance due to steeper tension softening material definition compared to smoother OOFEM response where plateau after tensile strength was used. Nevertheless, both models accurately predict maximum resistance, and both can be considered good. Overall assessment is that the results of both models are reasonably aligned and that both give sufficiently good results. OOFEM model predicts vertical displacements slightly better, due to modified material law in compression, lack of contact elements at the top and bottom, and slightly different effect of springs between the RC beams and steel supports.

- Pier P-R2R-1

Fig. 5.2 Direct comparison for pier sample P-R2R-1.

Both models capture diagonal shear with some flexural damage in the corners adequately. ABAQUS damage prediction shows steeper diagonal crack angle due to top and bottom separation contact definition between masonry and RC beams. The effect of separation contacts is also a more gradual decrease of resistance after peak resistance. Both models predict maximum resistance accurately. The shrinkage of the sides of the piers was better captured by the OOFEM. Overall, both simulations give reasonable results.

- Pier P-R2R-2

Fig. 5.3 Direct comparison for pier sample P-R2R-2.

Both models simulate diagonal shear cracking with substantial flexural damage in the corners. This response is the same as was observed in the experiments. However, ABAQUS predicts steeper diagonal crack and a more gradual decrease of resistance due to top and bottom separation contact between masonry and RC beams.

Both models predict maximum resistance accurately. However, the vertical shrinkage at the sides of the wall of both simulations is slightly different, and both are slightly different from the experiment. Nevertheless, both simulations sufficiently reproduce experimental results.

- Pier P-B2U

Fig. 5.4 Direct comparison for pier sample P-B2U.

Both models capture diagonal shear damage adequately. ABAQUS model shows steeper drop of pushover curve after maximum resistance due to steeper tension softening material definition compared to smoother OOFEM. Both models predict maximum resistance with accuracy. OOFEM model also shows a good match of vertical displacements.

- Pier P-B2R-1

Fig. 5.5 Direct comparison for pier sample P-B2R-1.

Simulations of both models predict diagonal shear with flexural damage at the corners, which is consistent with the tests. More gradual decrease of resistance in ABAQUS pushover curve is due to lower stiffness because of separation between masonry and RC beams. Both models slightly underpredict maximum resistance. The difference in both models most likely occurs because of strengthening of masonry due to connection of both leaves due to connectors, which was not directly taken into account in the models. OOFEM model also shows good match of vertical displacements.

- Pier P-B2R-2

Fig. 5.6 Direct comparison for pier sample P-B2R-2.

The results of both simulations adequately reproduce diagonal shear with extensive flexural damage in the corners. In this case, both models predict steep diagonal crack, which is in alignment with the experimental test. More gradual decrease of resistance in ABAQUS's pushover curve, due to definition of separation contacts between masonry and RC beams. Both models predict maximum resistance accurately. OOFEM model also shows accurate match of vertical displacements.

- Pier P-B1U

Fig. 5.7 Direct comparison for pier sample P-B1U.

The diagonal shear damage is adequately predicted by both numerical simulations, and the damage is aligned with the experimentally observed one. The pushover curves of both models are reasonable. The OOFEM model better simulates initial stiffness, but both models struggle with post peak response. The maximum resistance is predicted accurately in both models. The OOFEM model also shows good alignment of vertical displacements with the tests.

- Pier P-B1R-1

Fig. 5.8 Direct comparison for Pier sample P-B1R-1.

Both models predict diagonal shear with concentrated flexural damage in the corners, which is aligned with the observations from the tests. The peak resistance is underestimated by both simulations, but not by much. The post peak response seems slightly better in the ABAQUS simulation, but the vertical displacements are better simulated by the OOFEM.

5.2. In-plane behaviour of spandrels

- Spandrel S-R2U

Fig. 5.9 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-R2U.

In case of spandrels, ABAQUS simulations consistently show higher maximum resistance due to assumed higher tensile strength. On the other hand, OOFEM model, which uses lower tensile strength with a plateau in tension, predicts maximum resistance more accordingly (bounded lintel condition). Both models are susceptible to bending damage. Note that both homogeneous models cannot account directly for the interlocking effect, which particularly affects the behavior of unreinforced spandrels without ties. Shear damage is therefore somewhat limited and both simulations struggle with diagonal strains and horizontal strains.

- Spandrel S-R2R-1

ABAQUS model (by UL FGG)

OOFEM (by DIA - UNITS)

Fig. 5.10 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-R2R-1.

Both models fail to simulate long hardening that was observed in the test. However, the maximum resistance is predicted with satisfactory precision. ABAQUS model shows steeper degradation after maximum resistance, whereas OOFEM model shows longer hardening phase with more gradual degradation. This is due to tensile stress-strain diagram of masonry, where ABAQUS models have higher uncracked strength with steeper softening law and OOFEM models have lower strength with plateau afterwards.

Diagonal strains in the spandrel are predicted better in OOFEM, but both simulations predict large compressive strains, that were not recorded at all. The prediction of horizontal strains is quite good for both models.

- Spandrel S-R2R-2

Fig. 5.11 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-R2R-2.

OOFEM model gives a good pushover curve prediction, whereas ABAQUS model shows slight overestimation of maximum resistance and too high resistance in post peak phase. Both models are able to simulate longer hardening phase due to boundary conditions in that particular case, where left pier was not connected properly to RC beam due to failing of apparatus when simulating vertical pressure. Both models correctly predict bending damage, but ABAQUS struggles with diagonal and horizontal strains, while OOFEM, on the other hand, simulates them relatively well. However, OOFEM predicts the horizontal sliding in the opposite direction, while ABAQUS matches the experimental direction, although it overestimates the magnitude of the displacements.

- Spandrel S-B2U

ABAQUS model (by UL FGG)

OOFEM (by DIA - UNITS)

Fig. 5.12 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-B2U.

OOFEM model (unbounded jack arch condition) shows quite precise response of spandrel specimen when comparing pushover curve, whereas ABAQUS model shows overestimation of ductility, due to high ultimate strain used for the material definition. Both models are able to simulate relatively brittle failure. Both models show predominantly bending damage, and OOFEM predicts also small levels of shear damage. The horizontal sliding of the right support and horizontal strains are modelled quite well by both programs, while diagonal strains show evident discrepancies with the test.

- Spandrel S-B2R-1

ABAQUS model (by UL FGG)

OOFEM (by DIA - UNITS)

Fig. 5.13 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-B2R-1.

OOFEM simulation (reduced masonry parameter condition) gives quite good prediction of spandrel specimen response in terms of the pushover curve, whereas the ABAQUS simulation overestimates the ductility due to high ultimate strain in the tensile material response. Both models give good maximum resistance approximations and show bending and shear damage. The horizontal sliding of the right support is better simulated in OOFEM, and the horizontal strains are approximately simulated by ABAQUS and OOFEM. OOFEM diagonal tensile strains are in agreement with the experiments, but both simulations predict large compressive strains, that did not emerge in the experimental test. The prediction of horizontal strains is quite good for both models.

- Spandrel S-B1U

ABAQUS model (by UL FGG)

OOFEM (by DIA - UNITS)

Fig. 5.14 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-B1U.

The pushover curve is predicted quite well by the ABAQUS model, however even this simulation fails to simulate ductility due to the high ultimate strain used in the material constitutive law. OOFEM model (unbounded jack arch condition) is capable to approximately reproduce the brittle failure mode. Both models show good maximum resistance approximation and both show predominantly bending damage, with OOFEM model predicting also light a shear damage. The simulation of the movement of the right support is poor for ABAQUS model, and also the diagonal stains are not aligned with experiments. The horizontal strains are quite good predicted by OOFEM.

- Spandrel S-B1R-1

ABAQUS model (by UL FGG)

OOFEM (by DIA - UNITS)

Fig. 5.15 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-B1R-1.

Both models somewhat overestimate of resistance when taken into account the original masonry parameters. It was suspected that the repair of cracked masonry was not completely satisfactory, which reduced the strength of the masonry material. OOFEM simulation was performed also with reduced masonry material parameters, and gives good alignment with the tests. Also the horizontal sliding and horizontal strains are simulated with adequate alignment with tests, whereas diagonal strain predictions detect excessive compressive phenomena, not observed experimentally.

Both models show the same damage pattern – predominantly bending with light shear damage.

5.3. Final remarks

The numerical simulations generally succeeded in reproducing the capacity curves, the type and extent of damage, and other quantities measured in the experiments (such as the heel uplift of the piers and the horizontal movement of spandrel supports). The fairly good agreement between the simulations and the experiments serves to validate the developed numerical models.

The verification of the numerical simulations was performed by comparing the results from two different software programs using similar models. Here too, the similarity between the results of both programs was sufficient to confirm the modelling approach and reduce the likelihood of errors.

Following successful validation and verification, the models can now be used for their intended purpose: simulating structural components that have not been experimentally tested, thereby further enhancing the usefulness of CONSTRAIN strengthening.

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